

EFFECT OF FIBER LENGTH, TYPE, AND VOLUME FRACTION ON FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF DISCONTINUOUS CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The use of carbon/carbon composite (C/C) is essential for many high temperature applications such as aircraft brakes, interior of furnaces or carriers for metal hardening. C/C is manufactured via several high temperature process steps, which are expensive and time consuming. Till now the majority of all C/C applications are continuous fiber reinforced among others due to a lack of knowledge about the essential manufacturing parameters of short fiber C/C [1, 2].

This paper describes a parameter study of fiber length, fiber type, and fiber volume fraction on the flexural strength of short fiber C/C.

2 Experimental

The short fibers used in this investigation were cut with a self-made fiber cutting machine (cf. Fig. 1).

Short fibers were cut from a PAN-based continuous roving in fiber lengths of 6 mm, 9 mm, 12 mm, and 18 mm. For each cutting length at least two hundred short fibers were measured to qualify the fiber length. The quality requirement was that the nominal fiber length is included within the interval of mean length plus/minus one standard deviation.

Short fiber C/C plates were manufactured by mixing the short carbon fibers and phenolic resin. After mixing a hot molding process followed. The green bodies were pyrolyzed at 1173 K in inert atmosphere. The carbonized green bodies were densified by liquid pitch impregnation with subsequent pyrolysis. After three densification cycles a graphitization at 2273 K in inert atmosphere was carried out.

The quasi-isotropic in-plane orientation of the short-fiber C/C plates was ensured by measuring the specific electrical resistance $\rho_{\text{spec,QI}}$ in several directions (see Fig. 2). The specific electrical resistance was measured using the device shown in Fig. 3. A constant current of 1.0 A was applied between the outer contact tips. Voltage drop was measured between the inner contact tips. The specific electrical resistance is calculated according to equation (1), where U is the voltage, t the thickness of the measured C/C plate, and I the applied current [3].

$$\rho_{\text{spec,QI}} = (U \cdot t \cdot \pi) / (I \cdot \ln(2)) \quad (1)$$

The specific electrical resistance was examined for 360° in 15° angle intervals. Thus 24 directions were measured within a C/C plate (cf. Fig. 2). Each direction was determined two times.

After electrical measurements the short fiber C/C plates were cut into specimens of about 6 mm x 30 mm x 100 mm. These specimens were tested in a four point bending test setup in dependence on DIN EN 658-3, DIN EN 843-1, ASTM C 1161, and ASTM C 1341 (cf. Fig. 4). Bearing distance L was 80 mm. The crosshead speed was 1 mm/min.

Three different PAN based carbon fibers, one high modulus (HM) and two high tenacity (HT), were studied. The first high tenacity fiber HT1 had a different surface treatment than the second HT2. Additionally for HT2, different fiber volume fractions in green body state ($V_{\text{f,green body state}}$) of 40 % and 56 % were analyzed.

For each parameter set at least 20 specimens were measured in carbonized and graphitized state. The mean value and standard deviation is calculated on basis of the 20 measurements.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Cutting length

Fiber length was qualified for all four cutting lengths (6 mm, 9 mm, 12 mm, and 18 mm). As an example the fiber length distribution of 6 mm short fibers is shown in Fig. 5. In this case mean fiber length is about 5.8 mm. First standard deviation is ± 0.4 mm. Thus the quality criterion, regarding nominal fiber length, is fulfilled. Furthermore the other three cut fiber lengths met this requirement, too.

3.2 Planar-isotropy of short fiber C/C plates

Planar-isotropy of short fiber C/C plates was analyzed by determination of specific electrical resistance. This is possible due to electrical conductivity of C/C. The carbon matrix possesses a higher specific electrical resistance than the carbon fibers in fiber axis direction. Thereby the fiber distribution can be evaluated. If a certain direction is preferred, in terms of amount of fibers oriented in this direction, specific electrical resistance is lower in this direction. Whereas, if in plane no direction dependence of the specific electrical resistance is measured, the fibers are planar-isotropically oriented.

In Fig. 6 mean value of specific electrical resistance is shown for 24 directions, between 0° and 345° , of a short fiber C/C plate. The mean value plot exhibits an almost circular shape. As a result the specific electrical resistance is independent from the direction. Thus a planar-isotropic fiber distribution could be assumed.

3.3 Fracture behavior of short fiber C/C plates

Fracture behavior of C/C depends on the fiber type [1, 4-12]. This is also true for short fiber C/C (cf. Fig. 7). Material based on HT1 fibers showed brittle fracture behavior in carbonized state. The two other fiber types, HT2 and HM, exhibit a pseudo-

ductile fracture behavior in carbonized state. The fiber matrix interface (FMI) of the HT1 is so strong that no fiber pull-out or fiber bridging occurs during fracture. The FMIs of HT2 and HM allow crack deflection and dissipation of crack energy.

During graphitization stresses arise at the FMI. Reasons for the stresses are twofold: 1. mismatch of thermal expansion coefficients between carbon fiber and carbon matrix; 2. anisotropic thermal expansion of carbon fiber and isotropic thermal expansion of carbon matrix. In case of HT1 the FMI cannot compensate the mismatch. As a result the HT1 short fiber C/C plates are delaminated in graphitized state. Therefore no flexural strength is measured for HT1 plates in graphitized state (cf. Fig. 9). The FMI of HT2 and HM compensates the arising stresses and no delaminations are observed after graphitization.

3.4 Influence of fiber type and fiber length on flexural strength

Flexural strength is plotted as a function of fiber type and fiber length for carbonized in Fig. 8 and for graphitized stage in Fig. 9. The fiber type has a significant influence on flexural strength for all fiber lengths in carbonized and graphitized stage. Best mechanical properties are owned by HT2 short fiber C/C plates, followed by the HM fiber plates. HT1 fiber plates possess worst bending properties. This behavior is caused by the strength of the fiber matrix interfaces [1, 4-12].

Fiber length has no significant influence on the flexural strength either in carbonized or in graphitized state within the investigated parameter range. This indicates that even 18 mm long carbon fibers are shorter than the critical fiber length of current C/C [10].

Flexural strengths of graphitized state are lower than in carbonized state. Cause for the lowering is stress induced graphitization of matrix carbon at the FMI during graphitization process [1, 13-20].

3.5 Influence of fiber volume fraction on flexural strength

Flexural strength of HT2 short fiber C/C plates with a $V_{f, \text{green body state}}$ of 56 % and 40 % are different (cf. Fig. 10 and Fig. 11). The lower $V_{f, \text{green body state}} = 40$ %

exhibits better mechanical properties than $V_{f, \text{green body state}} = 56\%$ in carbonized and graphitized state. The reason for this behavior is, that the high $V_{f, \text{green body state}}$ shows an increase in thickness during the carbonization process. This is probably caused by too less matrix, which results in low binding strength perpendicular to the plate surface. Thus relaxation of the fibers is possible during pyrolysis. As observed for the different fiber types (see 3.4), flexural strengths of graphitized state are lower than in carbonized state for both fiber volume fractions. Root for the lowering is the stress induced graphitization of matrix carbon at the FMI during graphitization process [1, 13-20]. Therefore fiber volume fraction plays an important role for flexural strength of short fiber C/C plates.

Best flexural strength is achieved for a fiber length of 18 mm, fiber type HT2 and fiber volume fraction in green body state of 40%. This parameter setup has a flexural strength of 98 ± 22 MPa in carbonized state and 94 ± 23 MPa in graphitized state.

4 Conclusion

The effect of fiber length, fiber type, and fiber volume fraction on flexural strength was studied. Therefore short fibers, between 6 mm and 18 mm fiber length, were produced with self-made fiber cutting machine for three different fiber types. Planar-isotropic short fiber C/C plates were manufactured, which had 40% and 56% fiber volume fractions in green body state.

Fiber length has no significant influence on the flexural strength in range of 6 mm to 18 mm. Fiber type as well as fiber volume fraction have a significant impact on the flexural strength.

Maximum flexural strength was achieved for a short fiber C/C plates with fiber length of 18 mm, fiber type HT2 and a fiber volume fraction in green body state of 40%. This parameter setup has a flexural strength of 98 ± 22 MPa for carbonized state and 94 ± 23 MPa for graphitized state.

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Fig. 1. Self-made fiber cutting machine.

Fig. 2. Directions of specific electrical resistance on a measured planar-isotropic short fiber C/C plate.

Fig. 3. Specific electrical resistance measuring device.

Fig. 4. Four point bending test setup with bearing distance $L = 80$ mm.

Fig. 5. Fiber length distribution for 6 mm cutting length.

Fig. 6. Specific electrical resistance of a planar-isotropic short fiber C/C plate.

Fig. 7. Fracture behavior for the three different fiber types in carbonized state.

Fig. 8. Flexural strength of the three fiber types for 56% $V_{f,green\ body\ state}$ in carbonized state.

Fig. 9. Flexural strength of the three fiber types for 56% $V_{f,green\ body\ state}$ in graphitized state.

Fig. 10. Flexural strength of HT2 fiber for 40% and 56% V_{f,green body state} in carbonized state.

Fig. 11. Flexural strength of HT2 fiber for 40% and 56% V_{f,green body state} in graphitized state.